

Research Article

“Recane”- Upcycled Paper Sheets Using Waste Byproducts

Kartina Abu Bakar¹ *, Mohamad Azlan Shafiq Kassim², Dzayim Ieman Muhamad Fuad³, and Amarr Idham Suni⁴

¹ Intellectual Development Department, Centre for Continuing Education, University of Malaya, 63000 Cyberjaya; kartina.abubakar@um.edu.my; 0009-0004-5964-4334

² Centre for Continuing Education, Universiti of Malaya, 63000 Cyberjaya; udc233432@umced.edu.my; 0009-0004-8647-3235

³ Centre for Continuing Education, Universiti of Malaya, 63000 Cyberjaya; udb230011@umced.edu.my; 0009-0006-8272-0643

⁴ Centre for Continuing Education, Universiti of Malaya, 63000 Cyberjaya; udc230081@umced.edu.my; 0009-0006-8272-0643

* Correspondence: kartina.abubakar@um.edu.my, 017-8803428

Abstract: *The issue behind global wastage is well-known, yet the solution to it remains entirely difficult to solve. With many governments suggesting new policy on how certain products should be recycled to be used for better purposes, the responsibility also lies in the hands of every individual in a working society to work toward a zero-waste future. Paper contributes to wastage on a large scale as consumers require it for personal reasons such as schoolwork while organisations need paper in order to function efficiently. The nature of paper is that after it is written on or used in any capacity, it will be thrown away ultimately. When done on such a massive scale worldwide, the effects of wastage can be seen thoroughly. With such a major issue, a smart solution is required; upcycling of byproducts. By using products that would otherwise just be thrown away to create a wholly new and useful product for general consumers, public perception of green products and technology will become normalised. Recane is a green-thinking company which uses waste byproducts to produce paper sheets. The primary materials for the product are used paper and sugarcane bagasse; the fibrous material left after juicing a sugarcane. Recane places importance on the use of byproducts; to stand out as environmentally forward-thinking and, more specifically, proactively solve the issue of wastage and landfills. The main target market of the sugarcane paper is academic institutions, as consumption of paper is seen to be very high, and Recane can even serve to be a cheaper alternative to these organisations seeking to have a product of the same quality but at a lower cost. Ultimately, Recane is able to be extremely attractive in the modern market and landscape of society which has been growing increasingly conscious of the environment.*

Keywords: *wastage, paper, bagasse, upcycling.*

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13888386

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

Waste is an inevitable factor in society, as when a product expires its usefulness it will naturally be thrown away. This statement is relevant to byproducts such as bagasse, but most importantly to paper. Only 38% of all paper and cardboard waste is recycled, with 56% finding its way into landfills, while the remaining is burned (National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 2023). This statistic can be

quantified further when considering that as of 2024, according to The World Counts, an environmental organisation, 26% of all waste in landfills is made up of paper waste. The space occupied by landfills is immense, with growth only expected to expand in the coming decades as populations grow; ultimately waste and dumping of unnecessary materials will only increase. With landfills being so expansive, the amount of space vacated for it, which would otherwise be occupied by native wildlife, is also decimated to make way for the tonnes and tonnes of deposited waste. Effective use of waste has been an effort undertaken by several GLCs and NGOs in an effort to curb the crisis of waste management. Some paper-adjacent products are non-biodegradable, such as wet wipes and diapers, further complicating the issue by contributing to the waste. Other alternatives to waste management such as burning poses an even greater threat to the environment. The International Cryosphere Climate Initiative puts forward that burning waste openly contributes to climate change on the whole as produces greenhouse gases such as methane and carbon dioxide. The proactive effort to take is to commit to upcycling. This process involves reclaiming materials or products no longer in use and transforming them into materials or products of superior quality or utility (Ecomaison, 2023). By not contributing to unnecessary wastage, the cycle of waste can be totally cut. With paper being such a major part of landfills, Recane has taken the challenge of finding an alternative to paper that produces zero-waste, zero adverse effects to the environment in its production, while still maximising quality to the consumer and profitability. The utilisation of byproducts is vital to Recane's production process, primarily seeking to reduce the prominence of paper waste by creating paper sheets. Bagasse, the fibrous byproduct of sugarcane, is mixed with the paper to make a more attractive and viable product for consumer use which can create a paper alternative that can serve a wide range of purposes; writing, wiping, use in handicrafts and creating other paper products. With paper being the primary medium for communication in offices, academic institutions, and other organisations over an extremely broad category, it is vital that an alternative to paper must have the same characteristics and ease of use of regular pulp paper.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

Recane collects unwanted or used paper from recycling centres as well as individuals wanting to directly donate. The types of paper or paper-adjacent products are newspapers, cardboard, and generally used paper. The sugarcane bagasse is collected directly from sugarcane vendors, grocers, factories, and other suppliers using sugarcane who would normally throw away the byproduct, with it being a regular waste product of the sugar industry (Mahmud and Anannya, 2021).

Thus, the used materials are paper, bagasse, water, and an emulsifier which binds the paper-bagasse mixture together. Once the bagasse and paper are collected, cleaning of the items is done not only for sanitary purposes but to soften the material for processing. The components are then cut into processable chunks which are then blended together along with water. This creates a thick paste once mixed with an emulsifier, which Recane uses organic compounds, such as flour, as to avoid inorganic components in the production process. The thick paste is passed through a sieve to separate any unwanted material which may spoil the integrity or texture of the paper sheets, and afterwards spread thin onto a solid surface to be left to dry.

Figure 1. Prototype of Recane Paper Sheets. Still in its paste form before the sheet fully dries.

The end result of this being paper which is intact, hardy but flexible, and attractive in appearance. The ready paper sheets are able to be folded and maintain the same characteristics as ordinary paper, but have an entirely green process.

Figure 2. End product of Recane Paper Sheets, showcasing its multipurpose nature.

3. FINDINGS

Most importantly, an alternative to paper must be able to be produced at the same rate while maintaining the same quality at a same or lower cost. Recane Sheets, with its simple production process and clear steps, is able to mass-produce efficiently with no adverse effects to the environment. Sourcing for the products also assist in our objective of zero-waste as Recane only gathers waste byproducts. The quality standard of Recane Sheets is high; the differences between it and ordinary paper are negligible.

The Recane Team conducted a test run wherein the bagasse-paper sheets were distributed to faculty members in the University of Malaya along with students on campus. The test consisted of a writing trial and a flexibility trial. First, participants would try to write and feel the texture of the paper to see the viability of it in practical settings. The second would involve using the paper for applied purposes in an academic setting; creating envelopes and paper bags for students. Participants would then test for the integrity and quality of the paper.

Results from these tests yielded the Recane Sheet had the same quality and physical characteristics to pulp paper. The paper was easily written on and flexible, additionally being able to still be used after contact with liquids as seen in the integrity test. Thus, the bagasse-paper product serves its primary objective of replacing paper while maintaining a greener, and less costly, method of production.

4. DISCUSSION

The amount of waste now circulating in the world, along with related issues such as the expansion of the logging industry, has necessitated the need for a product which hands the responsibility of aiding the planet in a consumer's own hands instead of that of a faceless organisation or agency. Moreover, this creates a more tangible connection between the user and the product; with the consumer feeling that he has more of an effect to environmental change than other means.

Figure 3. The Recane Paper Sheet Logo.

Recane's primary business objective is to generate profit through the production and supplying of bagasse-paper sheets to sectors requiring paper in any capacity. In recent decades, the reputation of an organisation or company is heavily impacted by its stance on environmental issues. Recane takes advantage of this fact, supplying zero-waste paper to companies seeking to reduce their corporate carbon footprint. Additionally, Recane places large focus on academic institutions as heavy reliance of regular paper for examinations, documents, and ordinary notes for students plays a large part in paper wastage. Recane Paper Sheets are made to be priced at a lower rate than regular paper not only to stay competitive, but to be attractive to students who as a demographic use paper in bulk quantities. By specifically targeting businesses and academic institutions, Recane is able to put its efforts into creating quality paper fit for practical office use such as in official company documents and printing or faxing.

The production process and creation of the paper sheets does not create any lasting harmful effects to the environment. Sourcing of sugarcane is done so ethically and through third-parties (vendors, hawkers, grocers) to ensure that the current problems faced with logging on a massive scale are not repeated when replaced with sugarcane. This can also be seen in the sourcing of paper, as only used paper is considered fit for the process.

5. CONCLUSION

On the whole, upcycling to create products that can assist in reducing the adverse effects of society towards nature is a welcome concept in society. A deciding issue is that many people are ignorant of upcycling as a solution, with a survey conducted among millennials by Ecomaison stating that more than 60% of those surveyed were not aware of the concept.

Recane, and the creation of the Recane Sheet, hope not only to raise awareness of global wastage and the reasons we should be more caring towards the Earth, but also to instil a sense of urgency in society that every individual has the power in his own hands to enact change and create a product which will have long-lasting effects to our everyday life. The more people aware of the responsibility of being in a society surrounded by nature, the closer Recane is to its mission of aiding in achieving a global mindset against waste.

Acknowledgments: A debt of gratitude is owed to Recane's advisor, Mrs. Kartina of University Malaya, for her endless support and guidance throughout the creation of the product and the extended abstract. Mrs. Kartina's mentorship throughout this project has been invaluable to the progress and outcome of what the Recane Team has created. Recane would also like to extend thanks to our sister group for this competition, Comfert, whose members served as a sounding board for Recane's ideas and vice versa. The Comfert Team's thoughts and opinions eased burdens of the creative process, though Recane is still dedicated to its own visions. Without the assistance and faith of both mentioned parties, Recane would not have been able to fully expand upon its vision.

References

- National Renewable Energy Laboratory. (2023). News Release: NREL Research Quantifies Losses from Cardboard, Paper Waste Latest in Series of Journal Articles on Landfilled Materials Quantifies Problem, Details Opportunities. Retrieved from: <https://www.nrel.gov/news/press/2023/news-release-nrel-research-quantifies-losses-from-cardboard-paper-waste.html>
- International Cryosphere Climate Initiative. (2024). Open Burning. Retrieved from: <https://iccinet.org/open-burning/#:~:text=Open%20field%20and%20forest%20burning,snow%20and%20ice%2C%20speeding%20melting.>
- The World Counts. (2024). Paper Waste Facts. Retrieved from: <https://www.theworldcounts.com/stories/paper-waste-facts>

Md. Arif Mahmud and Ferdausee Rahman Anannya. (2021). Sugarcane bagasse - A source of cellulosic fibre for diverse applications. National Library of Medicine. Retrieved from:
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8379461/#:~:text=Sugarcane%20bagasse%20is%20a%20fibrous,comes%20from%20the%20sugar%20industry.>

Ecomaison. (2023). Recycling, upcycling, reusing: Millennials want to be encouraged! Retrieved from:
<https://ecomaison.com/en/espace-presse/recyclage-upcycling-reemploi/>